

Effects of Atmospheric Air on the Human Body

Razikova Dilnoza Kadirovna
Bukhara State Medical Institute

Abstract: Over the past decades, issues related to protecting the atmosphere from pollution have become particularly relevant. Successful solution to the problem of improving the health of the air basin largely depends on an adequate assessment of the state of atmospheric air pollution, which is the basis for the development and adoption of measures to minimize negative environmental consequences.

Key points: air, pollution, natural environment, pollutants, urban ecosystems.

In the current situation, it seems extremely important (both for immediate practical actions and for long-term planning) to have a well-organized monitoring system, a special information system - a system of observations, analysis and forecast of the state of atmospheric air.

Compared to other objects of the natural environment (water, soil , vegetation), atmospheric air is characterized by high spatial mobility and a high degree of distribution of pollutant emissions , which, along with the variety of ways in which harmful substances enter the atmosphere, makes the task of organizing a monitoring network complex and multifaceted,

The creation of a scientifically based atmospheric air monitoring system involves solving many problems, the main of which are planning a spatial observation network and determining the list of pollutants subject to mandatory control.

Timely and reliable information about the state of the natural environment is the basis for developing optimal management decisions in the field of nature conservation, as well as for assessing their effectiveness. The results of studies of the role of ecological and geographical factors in the formation of pollution levels and the transfer of harmful substances, as well as their redistribution between environments, have important methodological significance for organizing a monitoring system.

Large cities, due to the maximum concentration of technogenic loads on the biotic environment, are characterized by directed changes in almost all of its components. The city forms unique meso- and microclimatic regimes and the corresponding technogenic-cultural landscape, the impact of which is often unfavorable for the population.

Human economic activity, especially in recent decades, has led to environmental pollution with industrial waste. The air, water and soil of urban ecosystems contain pollutants, the concentration of which often exceeds the maximum permissible concentration (MPC), which negatively affects public health. In recent decades, there has been an increase in certain nosological forms of diseases, which is caused by environmental pollution. The main reason for these phenomena is the global environmental crisis caused by the greenhouse effect, acid rain, pollution of the planet with supertoxicants, a decrease in ozone concentration in the upper layers of the atmosphere, etc.

The global environmental crisis is caused by spontaneous human intervention in natural processes. It is a consequence of the totality of economic activities of civilization and manifests itself in changes in the characteristics of the natural environment on a planetary scale, and therefore poses a serious danger to life on Earth.

Due to the systemic nature of the ecosphere, any human impact on the natural environment results in a reciprocal impact of nature on society. "The history of human influence on the biosphere shows that technological progress is constantly increasing the possibilities of impact on the environment, creating the preconditions for major environmental crises." "According to the law of reflection, this negative impact is stronger, the more significant the human intervention." Therefore, this problem can be considered solved only if production waste (emissions, discharges into the environment) produced by humanity are minimized to a level that the nature of the Earth can cope with on its own.

Solving global environmental problems is impossible without identifying the laws of interaction between society and the natural environment, which will make it possible to make reliable forecasts for the development of the "society - man - technology - natural environment" system and take timely measures to eliminate or weaken contradictions between society and the natural environment. Therefore, in the context of the global environmental crisis, issues of managing environmental quality on the basis of effectively existing laws, regulations, etc. become particularly relevant.

Atmospheric air is one of the main components of the environment, and to solve the problem of managing its quality, it is necessary to study the processes of formation of the level of pollution and its changes under the influence of meteorological and heliophysical factors .

In the era of scientific and technological progress, anthropogenic impacts on the atmosphere are becoming more intense and large-scale. The consequences of air pollution are a serious geo-ecological problem for large industrial enterprises and adjacent areas.

In this regard, issues of objective quality control and regulation of the state of the atmosphere become of greatest importance. In order to ensure scientifically based management of air quality in these territories, regular and prompt information is needed on emissions of harmful substances into the atmosphere, on levels of pollution, their changes over a long period, as well as on meteorological conditions accompanying the spread of pollutants in the atmosphere . In this regard, one of the most pressing problems is the development and improvement of monitoring of air pollution by specific types of anthropogenic sources.

The air basin plays a leading role in all planetary processes. The increasing scale of anthropogenic impact on the natural environment (high rates of energy development, increasing volume of transport services, developing technologies, etc.) at the present stage requires increased attention to the processes of atmospheric air protection. Currently, a global environmental crisis caused by anthropogenic pollution is already raging. In recent years, significant imbalances in the balance of the biosphere have been clearly visible.

Modern technological processes greatly disturb the balance of the biosphere. Environmental pollution is caused mainly by processes associated with the generation of electricity, vehicles, agricultural production, the functioning of the manufacturing industry and public utilities. "It may seem," said Academician V.A. Kirillin, "that hundreds of millions of tons of pollution entering the atmosphere annually and constituting less than one ten-thousandth of a percent of the weight of atmospheric air are just a drop in the bucket. However, this is far from the case. is that, firstly, over time the amount of air pollutants accumulates, secondly, air pollutants are distributed unevenly and in some places their concentration is already unacceptably high, thirdly, even very small concentrations of some substances are dangerous."

The human body is influenced by many factors of different nature, which leads to various changes in the health indicators of children and adults. According to published data, human health depends 50% on lifestyle, 20% on the state of the environment, 20% on heredity and 10% on medicine. The most significant in shaping the risks of developing adverse health effects at different stages of children's ontogenetic development are: in the first year of a child's life - biological factors, at preschool age - social factors and at school age - environmental factors, as well as conditions associated with educational process and organization of nutrition at school. Also, the health status of

children and adolescents is determined by their adaptive capabilities, which depend on biological factors (heredity, age, gender) and environmental conditions (nutrition, physical activity, social well-being, lifestyle). In addition, factors in the technogenic ecological environment have a significant impact on the health indicators of children and adults. The highest technogenic load on the environment is created in industrial regions, including the Donbass (Donetsk and Lugansk regions) with large-scale ferrous metallurgy, coke chemistry, coal mining and processing industries, and thermal power facilities. According to research results, living in conditions of high technogenic load has a negative impact on the health of children and adults .

Goal and tasks. The main goal is to optimize the existing atmospheric air monitoring network and increase its representativeness.

Objectives of the study .

1. Comprehensive assessment of the level of air pollution in industrial centers of the Republic of Uzbekistan.
2. Study of the climatic regime of meteorological quantities and phenomena that determine the dispersion and accumulation of pollutant emissions on the territory of the Republic of Uzbekistan.
3. Study of the influence of meteorological quantities and phenomena, heliophysical factors on the formation of the level of atmospheric pollution and the prevalence of diseases in the population .

Scientific novelty. The construction of a representative network for monitoring air quality is influenced by the conditions of each city, i.e. the scale of anthropogenic impact on the environment, natural and climatic conditions and the economic specialization of the city.

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